

MICROHARDNESS OF A PE / PE – COMPOSITE AND POLYETHYLENE GRADIENT MATERIAL

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SUMMARY: This paper presents characteristics of polyethylene gradient material and polyethylene fibre/polyethylene matrix composites determined by universal hardness tests. PE-samples with a gradient in molecular weight (MW) and polyethylene / polyethylene composites were characterised by light microscopy and microhardness measurements. The influence of molecular weight, molecular weight distribution (MWD), the morphology and the properties of the composites were studied. An increase in molecular weight of polyethylene in the graded samples leads to a decrease in hardness and indentation modulus. In the polyethylene homocomposites an increase in microhardness HU_{corr} and indentation modulus Y_{HU} can be observed with an increasing orientation of the molecular chains. The mechanical work indicated during the indentation procedure was investigated: partly consumed as plastic deformation work and partly set free as work of the reverse deformation. In this paper the results of mechanical tests will be discussed in view of the potential improvements in wear and durability of knee joint replacements.

KEYWORDS: universal microhardness; UHMWPE fibres; polyethylene homocomposites; polyethylene gradient material, total knee replacement.

INTRODUCTION:

Ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) is widely used in many orthopaedic implant applications such as total hip, shoulder and knee joint replacements. It is utilised because of superior mechanical properties and biocompatibility. The wear of UHMWPE in artificial joints is a major reason for long-term osteolysis resulting in loosening of endoprostheses. The resistance of polyethylene inserts against abrasive wear, pitting and delamination may be improved using a UHMWPE-fibre reinforced high density polyethylene (HDPE) combined with a surface of UHMWPE (Fig. 1). The conjunction between UHMWPE-fibres/HDPE and UHMWPE can be achieved by a transition zone of polyethylene with a gradually increasing molecular weight (molecular weight gradient).

Fig. 1: Design of a wear optimized PE-component

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Different grades of high-density polyethylene (HDPE) and ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) were used for manufacturing a gradient in molecular weight (Table 1). The commercial grades of polyethylene samples were produced by Billetter Kunststoffpulver AG (Germany), DSM (The Netherlands), Hoechst AG (Germany), Solvay (Belgium) and Ticona GmbH (Germany). Ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) fibres, Dyneema[®] SK 65 (kindly supplied by DSM), were used as reinforcement.

Table 1.: Molecular weight, molecular weight distribution (data of producer statements) and tensile properties of commercial PE grades (gradient III).

Gradient III				
PE	MW [g/mole]	MWD	E [MPa]	σ_s [MPa]
DHD3H173	80.000	5	1655	28.3
SHD2020	114.700	8,5	978	27.3
DHD7625	180.000	20	1216	28.9
HHD8020	490.000	27	783	20.5
HHD8110	700.000	-	1060	26.1
DUH210	1.460.000	-	608	19.2
HUH1120	4.000.000	13	708	22.7

Testing

Samples for both light and AFM microscopy were prepared by cryo-microtome cutting. AFM was carried out with the NanoScope[®] III (Digital Instruments, Santa Barbara, CA). Microhardness and indentation modulus were measured according to DIN 50359-1 at room temperature using a Fischerscope[®] tester H100VP XY-Prog with a Vickers square pyramidal diamond indenter (MK269) with a load of 0.002 N. The microhardness HU_{corr} and indentation modulus Y_{HU} were calculated by measuring the indentation depth electronically with the equipment and were related to the geometry of the indenter.

Tensile tests were performed on the bulk materials with a computerised universal testing machine (Zwick 1445) at a crosshead speed of 10 mm/min.

Manufacture of the polyethylene homocomposite and the PE-gradient material

F. v. Lacroix presented a manufacturing route and the corresponding mechanical properties of polyethylene fibre (Dyneema[®] SK65, DSM) / polyethylene matrix composites [1 and 2]. The PE / PE composites investigated were manufactured applying this technique. Fig. 2 shows an AFM surface plot of the UHMWPE-fibre / HDPE matrix composite. The SK65 fibres have a kidney form and are shown here in the wet PE powder impregnation technique [1] of fibre bundles.

Fig. 2: AFM image of UHMWPE-fibre reinforced HDPE

PE-samples with a gradient in molecular weight, within a range of $8 \cdot 10^4$ - $4 \cdot 10^6$ g/mole, were prepared by compression moulding of the polyethylene powders. The powder was stacked in the mould and kept under a pressure of 20 MPa. The pressure applied on the melt was then decreased to 1.5 MPa. The compression moulding cycle included heating the stacked powder under pressure, keeping the melt at a steady state temperature and pressure for 30-90 min, and finally cooling down of the mould and the gradient material under a continuous pressure of 10 MPa. The steady state temperature was varied from 140 °C at the base plate (HDPE-side) to 200 °C at the piston (UHMWPE-side). The pressure and thermal cycle were optimised for each component configuration.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The microhardness reflects changes in morphology and microstructure of polyethylenes which, in turn, are monitoring the macroscopic mechanical properties of these materials. The microhardness of PE is directly correlated with material and structural parameters, such as MW, MWD, crystallinity, degree of branching, lamellar thickness and the number of molecular entanglements [3-5]. It is therefore suitable for the characterisation of a polyethylene gradient.

Fig. 3 shows the bright field micrographs of a Vickers indentation in the cross section of a fibre. Cross sections, perpendicular to the fibre direction, were examined in order to spatially elucidate the structural development during compression moulding. A uniform transcrystal-

line interphase was found to develop on the boundary between the HDPE-matrix and the UHMWPE-fibre. The application of the low test loads resulted in small indentations enabling the microhardness measurements both in the fibre and in the transcrystalline zone between fibre and matrix for the first time.

Fig. 3: Bright field micrograph of Vickers indentation in the UHMWPE-fibres / HDPE-matrix composite.

The influence of the chain orientation and MW on microhardness and indentation modulus of UHMWPE-fibre / HDPE-matrix composite and PE gradient III is shown in Fig. 4. An increase in the molecular weight of polyethylene leads to a decrease in hardness and indentation modulus in the graded samples.

Fig. 4: Universal hardness HU_{corr} and indentation modulus $Y_{HU0.002}$ of an UHMWPE-fibre / HDPE-matrix composite and PE-gradient.

The microhardness and indentation moduli divide gradient III into two groups. In the first group are HDPE's (DHD 3H173, SHD 2020, DHD 7625) with a microhardness between 90-115 MPa. In the second group are the high and ultra high molecular weight polyethylenes (HHD 8020, HHD 8110, DUH 210 and HUH 1120) with HU_{corr} between 55-70 MPa. This result corresponds to the application of commercial polyethylenes.

As expected, here the UHMWPE fibres achieve the highest HU_{corr} and Y_{HU} values of all examined PE materials. In the polyethylene homocomposite both HU_{corr} and Y_{HU} increase with increasing molecular orientation:

HU_{corr}, Y_{HU} (UHMWPE-fibre) \gg HU_{corr}, Y_{HU} (transcrystalline interphase) $>$ HU_{corr}, Y_{HU} (matrix).

The mechanical work W_t indicated during the indentation procedure is partly consumed as plastic deformation work W_r . During the removal of the test force the remaining part is set free as work of the reverse deformation.

The influence of the chain orientation and MW on the total mechanical work W_t indicated during the indentation procedure, plastic deformation work W_r and elastic reverse deformation W_e of the UHMWPE-fibre / HDPE-matrix composite and the PE-gradient are shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5: The total mechanical work indicated during the indentation procedure W_t , plastic deformation work W_r and elastic reverse deformation W_e of an UHMWPE-fibre / HDPE-matrix composite and PE-gradient.

68% of the total mechanical work W_t in HDPE's (DHD 3H173, SHD 2020, DHD 7625) was used as plastic deformation work W_r and the remaining work was set free as elastic back deformation W_e . In the group of the high and ultra high molecular weight polyethylenes (HHD 8020, HHD 8110, DUH 210 and HUH 1120) 65.5 % of the total mechanical work W_t was consumed as plastic deformation work W_r and the remaining 34.5 % was set free as elastic

reverse deformation W_e . This group indicates quantitatively the highest values of mechanical work, plastic deformation work and work of the reverse deformation of all investigated PE. In the PE fibre, however, almost 85% of the W_t was used up by plastic deformation work W_p and only 15 % by elastic reverse deformation W_e , compared to 30 % and 70 % in the transcrystalline interphase and 29 % and 71 % in the matrix, respectively. That can be attributed to the fibril structure of the UHMWPE - fibres. Accordingly the elastic reverse deformation is about 50 % smaller as in all other polyethylenes.

CONCLUSION

The microhardness of melt crystallised samples with a polyethylene gradient in molecular weight and polyethylene homocomposites was investigated and characterised. The universal microhardness and indentation modulus in a PE gradient increases with decreasing molecular weight. In the fibre reinforced part of the gradient material HU_{corr} and Y_{HU} increase further; indicated by an increasing orientation of the molecular chains. The total mechanical work of the UHMWPE fibres measured, however, shows the lowest values of all examined PEs. The high and ultra high molecular weight polyethylenes quantitatively indicate the highest values of mechanical work, plastic deformation work and work of the reverse deformation of all PE investigated.

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